

SUPERSATURATION COEFFICIENT AND THE DIFFERENTIAL HEAT OF SOLUTION

BY B. S. SRIKANTAN AND C. N. VENKATACHALLUM

An equation has been derived for the calculation of heat of solution of saturated solutions from supersaturation coefficient and limits of supersaturation. The values for KCl, NH₄Cl, KNO₃ and KClO₄ agree with those calculated from Williamson's equation.

It has been shown by Srikantan and Ramachandra (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 585) that vant Hoff's isochore could be used to calculate the heat of solution of saturated solutions of substances whose temperature coefficient of solubility is constant; but for substances like NH₄Cl, KClO₄ and KNO₃, whose temperature coefficient of solubility is not constant, the equation becomes inapplicable. Ostwald-Freundlich equation (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, 34, 495; "Kapillarchemie", Leipzig, 1909, p. 144) for supersaturated solution can be rewritten as

$$T_s \left(\frac{S - S_n}{S_n} \right) = \left(\frac{2 M \sigma}{R d \tau} \right) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $(S - S_n/S_n)$ is the supersaturation coefficient, S_n is the solubility at temperature T_s (abs.), M is the molecular weight of the solute, d is density, τ is the size of solute particle and σ is the free surface energy of solute particles at T .

Jones and Partington's equation (*Phil. Mag.*, 1945, 29, 35) for supercooling for spontaneous crystallisation, when the amount of dissolved solute is constant, gives the following relation

$$\lambda \left(\frac{T_s - T_0}{T_s} \right) = \frac{2 M \sigma}{d \tau} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where λ is the heat of saturated solution in cal./g. mol., T_s is the temperature of saturation in degrees absolute, T_0 is the temperature of spontaneous crystallisation on cooling a saturated solution.

Combining (1) and (2) one gets the relation

$$\lambda = R T_s^2 \left(\frac{S - S_n}{S_n} \right) \times \frac{1}{(T_s - T_0)} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

connecting heat of solution and supersaturation coefficient and the limit of supersaturation.

Williamson (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1944, 40, 435) proposed the following equation

$$\Delta_{\text{Sat.}} (H_{\text{soln.}}) = R T_s^2 \left(\frac{dm}{dt} \right)_{\text{sat}} \times \left(\frac{1}{m} \right)_{\text{sat}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where ΔH is the heat of solution of saturated solution at T and dm is the small change in concentration of saturated solution for a small change of temperature dt and m is the concentration of the saturated solution at T . The following table gives the data calculated by equations (3) and (4) for KCl, NH_4Cl , KNO_3 and KClO_4 .

λ cal./g. is the heat of solution calculated by equation (3). The values of supersolubility coefficient $S - S_0/S_0$ are taken from a previous paper of the authors (this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 608) and $T_s - T_0$ are from the data of one of us (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 627) the relevant values being adopted for different regions. ΔH cal./g. mol. is the heat of solution calculated by equation (4); dt is taken as 10° , being 5° on either side of T , and dm , the change in solubility and m is the average solubility in that interval. The solubility data from International Critical Tables (Vol. V, p. 169) have been used.

TABLE I

Temp.	$S - S_0/S_0$	λ cal./g. mol.	ΔH cal./g. mol.
1. KCl. $T_s - T_0 = 13.1$			
30°	0.1038	1440	1440
40°	0.0921	1400	1360
45°	0.0877	1350	1340
2. KNO_3 . $T_s - T_0 = 3.9$ till 40° and 7.8 from 40° to 70° .			
20°	0.1591	6920	6620
50°	0.2253	5970	5750
60°	0.2011	5770	5380
3. NH_4Cl . $T_s - T_0 = 3.7$ between 10° and 40° & = 5.3 between 50° and 60° .			
20°	0.0459	2210	1900
30°	0.0450	2210	1950
55°	0.0434	1940	1840
4. KClO_4 . $T_s - T_0 = 6.2$ till 20° and 2.6 above 20° .			
10°	0.3109	7950	7020
30°	0.1098	7670	6860
40°	0.0896	6900	6440
50°	0.0825	6610	7350

The values of λ , heat of saturated solution, by the present equation at different temperatures agree with those of ΔH obtained from Williamson's equation. In both the equations the activity factor has not been introduced. The interionic attraction in supersaturated solutions will be greater than that for saturated solutions.